

RESISTANCE BRAZING OF SICP/AL COMPOSITE

J. Zhang¹, J. Yu¹, S. Meng² and X.B. Zeng¹

¹ *Analysis and Measuring Center, Harbin Institute of Technology,
Harbin 150001, P.R. China*

² *Beijing Spacecrafts, Chinese Academy of Space Technology,
Beijing 100080, P.R. China*

SUMMARY: The SiCp/Al composite plate was fabricated by powder metallurgy and rolling. Resistance brazing of the SiCp/Al composite was carried out by a Gleeble-1500 Thermal Mechanical Simulator. Al, Al-Zn-Mg-Si, Cu, Zn-Al and Zn-Sn-Cu were adopted as interlayer materials. The properties of the joint were measured and the microstructure was observed by electron microscope. It was found that the properties of the joints with interlayer of Al, Al-Zn-Mg-Si or Cu is lower, while the shear strength of the joint with a interlayer of Zn-Sn-Cu is 76 MPa, which is almost the same as the strength of the interlayer. Therefore, the effects of welding parameters (temperature, pressure and interlayer thickness) on the shear strength of the joint with the interlayer of Zn-Sn-Cu were studied in detail. The strength of the joint with a interlayer of Zn-Al is influenced by the composition of the agent for eliminating the oxide film on the composite surface, and especially, greatly depends on the welding parameters which is hardly controlled precisely.

KEYWORDS: silicon carbide, particle, aluminum, interlayer, brazing.

INTRODUCTION

Silicon carbide particle reinforced aluminum (SiCp/Al) composites have potential advantages such as high properties and low cost, and therefore have a strong application future in many fields. Many works have been done about the fabrication techniques, plastic deformation behavior, microstructure and properties of the SiCp/Al composites. However, welding technique of this composite is still a big problem which limits its applications in many aspects. The great difference of the physical and chemical properties between matrix and reinforcement in the SiCp/Al composite results in a low weldability of the SiCw/Al composite [1].

There are a few reports about the welding of the SiCp/Al composites [2,3], from which it can be seen that brazing is a feasible route for welding this composite. There are two main advantages of the brazing of the SiCp/Al composite: (1) there is a small damage to the matrix materials because of the low temperature during brazing; and (2) The brazing interlayer material will be melted and squeezed out of the welding seam together with the oxide film, which improves the wettability between the interlayer and matrix materials.

A resistance brazing route was adopted in this research for welding the SiCw/Al composite. The welded specimens can be heated at a very high speed, and a higher pressure can be applied, so a good bonding of the SiCw/Al composites can be expected.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The SiCp/Al composite was fabricated by powder metallurgy technique. The reinforcement is SiC particle with average diameter of 10 μ m, and the matrix is 2024Al. The SiCp/Al composites were joined by the resistance braze welding technique, and the effect of interlayer and welding parameter on the microstructure and shear strength of the joint was investigated. The microstructure and elemental distribution at the joints were observed and measured by EPMA, and the fracture surfaces were observed by SEM.

Table 1: Optimum shear strength of the joints with different interlayers

Interlayer material	Al	Al-Zn-Mg-Si	Cu	Zn-Sn-Cu	Zn-Al
Melting point (°C)	660	547~568	1083 (548)*	200~350	430~500
Shear strength (MPa)	33.5	13.5	<10	77.5	-

*:Melting point of Al-Cu eutectic alloy is 548 °C.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

On the one hand, in order not to damage the matrix composite, the welding temperature should not be higher than 505°C, which is the solidus temperature of 2024Al. On the other hand, the interlayer should be melted to get a tightly connect. Five kinds of materials (shown in Table 1) were adopted as the interlayer, while Al, Al-Zn-Mg-Si and Cu were found not suitable as the interlayer material in the resistance braze welding of the SiCp/Al composite. The most important reason is that the three kinds of materials can not be melted at the temperatures lower than 505°C.

When Al was used as interlayer material, the SiCp/Al composite was welded in the conditions that interlayer thickness of 10~60 μ m, temperatures of 460~540°C, pressure of 23~38MPa and time of 3s. After 20 times of welding tests in the condition within the parameter range above, it was found that the shear strength of the joint is very low, and the maximum value is 33.5MPa. Because the melting point of Al is too high to be melted at the temperatures from 460°C to 540°C, the interlayer can not be squeezed out of the welding seam, and therefore the oxide file can not eliminated, leading to a low joint strength. Fig.1 is the morphology of the joint and the distribution of Si and Al across the joint. It can be seen that there is a distinguished interface between the interlayer and matrix material (Fig.1a) and no elemental diffusion can be found (Fig.1b). This indicates that this joint is a kind of mechanical bonding, which results in a low shear strength of the joint.

When Al-Zn-Mg-Si was used as interlayer material, the SiCp/Al composite was welded in the conditions that interlayer thickness of 80~100 μ m, temperatures of 470~530°C, pressure of 16~32MPa and time of 2s. After 8 times of welding tests, it was found that the shear strength of the joint is even lower than that with Al interlayer, and the maximum value is only 13.5MPa. Although the melting point of Al-Zn-Mg-Si is lower than Al, it is still too high to be melted at the temperatures from 470°C to 530°C, which leads to a low joint strength because of the same reason. On the other hand, the plastic deformation of the Al-Zn-Mg-Si is more hard than that of Al, leading to a lower bonding strength compared with that of the joint with Al interlayer.

Fig.1: EPMA morphology (a) of the joint and the distribution of Si and Al (b) across the joint with a interlayer of Al.

When Cu was used as interlayer material, the SiCp/Al composite was welded in the conditions that interlayer thickness of 35~75µm, temperatures of 450~500°C, pressure of 25MPa and time of 2s. It was found that the shear strength of the joint is very low, and the maximum value is lower than 10MPa, which indicates that the SiCp/Al composite is almost not connected. If the Al-Cu eutectic alloy is formed at the interface between Cu interlayer and the SiCp/Al composite, the melting point of the Al-Cu eutectic alloy is only 548°C, and a good bonding may be formed in this case. However, no Al-Cu eutectic alloy is formed in this experimental condition, so the SiCp/Al composite can not be welded with Cu interlayer in this condition.

Zn-Sn-Cu alloy are the most desirable interlayer materials, and an optimum shear strength of 76 MPa was obtained.

The effect of welding parameters on the microstructure and shear strength of the joint with a Zn-Sn-Cu interlayer was studied. The shear strength of the joint firstly increases with increasing welding temperature from 370°C to 410°C and then gradually decrease from 420°C to 440°C, as shown in Fig.2. With increasing temperature, the flowability of the Zn-Sn-Cu alloy increases, which makes it easier for the interlayer material to be squeezed out of the welding seam together with the oxide film. So the shear strength of the joint increases with increasing temperature. However, when the temperature is higher than 420°C, the shear strength of the joint decreases with increasing temperature because of the more serious oxidization.

Fig.3 is fracture surfaces of the welded specimens with a 40µm thick Zn-Sn-Cu interlayer. Under a same pressure (15MPa), when the temperature is lower (370°C, as shown in Fig.3a) lots of area was broken between the interlayer and the matrix, because some oxide film can not be eliminated; while at higher temperature (410°C, as shown in Fig.3b), only a few area was broken at the interface, and most of the fracture takes place in the interlayer.

Fig. 2: Effect of welding temperature on the shear strength of the joint with a interlayer of Zn-Sn-Cu

Fig. 3: SEM photographs of the fracture surface of the welded specimens with a 40µm thick Zn-Sn-Cu interlayer, (a) $T=370^{\circ}\text{C}$, $P=15\text{MPa}$; (b) $T=410^{\circ}\text{C}$, $P=15\text{MPa}$, (c) $T=410^{\circ}\text{C}$, $P=30\text{MPa}$.

With increasing welding pressure, the joint shear strength firstly increases from 12MPa to 25MPa, and becomes constant when the pressure is higher than 25MPa, as shown in Fig.4. With increasing pressure, more and more oxide film can be eliminated, and when the pressure is higher than 25MPa, all the fracture takes place in the interlayer, so the joint strength becomes constant. This analysis can be proved from the comparison between Fig.3b and Fig.3c.

Interlayer thickness is also a very important factor to influence the joint shear strength. From Fig.5 it can be seen that the joint shear strength decreases with increasing interlayer thickness from 40µm to 100µm. This is mainly because that with decreasing interlayer thickness the elemental diffusion becomes easier, and the diffusion bonding will contribute to the high joint strength.

Fig. 4: Effect of welding pressure on the shear strength of the joint with a interlayer of Zn-Sn-Cu

Fig.5: Effect of thickness of the Zn-Sn-Cu interlayer on the shear strength of the joint

An optimum shear strength of the joint was obtained by the resistance braze welding with a Zn-Sn-Cu interlayer (40µm in thickness) under the pressure of 25MPa at 420°C. At this condition, a good connect between SiCp/Al composite and the interlayer was obtained as shown in Fig.6(a). The elemental distribution shown in Fig.6(b) indicates that there is a little elemental diffusion at the interface, which leads to a higher bonding strength .

Zn-Al alloy was also adopted as the interlayer material for welding the SiCp/Al composite. The liquidus temperature is 500°C, which is only 5°C lower than the solidus temperature of 2024Al, so it is very difficult to precisely control the welding temperature. On the other hand, the strength of the joint with a interlayer of Zn-Al is greatly influenced by the composition of the agent for eliminating the oxide film on the composite surface. In this test, we can not get good result because of above reason and also because it is difficult to get very thin Zn-Al alloy film. However, it is believed that Zn-Al alloy is one of the most suitable interlayer material for welding the SiCp/Al composite.

Fig.6: EPMA results of the joint: (a) morphology of the joint, (b) elemental distribution at the joint.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Al, Al-Zn-Mg-Si and Cu is not suitable for brazing the SiCp/Al composite. The joint strength is very low because the three kinds of materials can not be melted at the temperature lower than 505°C.
2. Zn-Sn-Cu alloy is suitable for the brazing of the SiCp/Al composite, and a shear strength of 76MPa was obtained, which reaches the strength of the interlayer.
3. The effect of welding parameters on the joint properties was studied with a interlayer of Zn-Sn-Cu alloy. The shear strength of the joint firstly increases with increasing welding temperature from 370°C to 410°C and then gradually decrease from 420°C to 440°C; with increasing welding pressure, the joint shear strength firstly increases from 12MPa to 25MPa, and becomes constant when the pressure is higher than 25MPa; the joint shear strength decreases with increasing interlayer thickness from to 40µm to 100µm.
4. The strength of the joint with a interlayer of Zn-Al is influenced by the composition of the agent for eliminating the oxide film on the composite surface, and especially, greatly depends on the welding parameters which is hardly controlled precisely.

REFERENCES

1. “What’s Being done to Weld Metal-Matrix Composite”, *Welding Journal*, June, 1991, pp. 65.
2. Devletion, J.H., “SiC/Al Metal Matrix Composite Welding by a Capacitor Discharge Process”, *Welding Journal*, June, 1987, pp. 33.
3. Guo, Y., “Brazing of Al-C Fiber Composite”, *Journal of Welding*, No.4, 1993, pp. 233 (in Chinese).